

Ascorbic Acid—The US Tariff Commission reports that 1.3 million pounds of ascorbic acid were produced by US manufacturers in December, 1971.

This raises the total figure on production for 1971 to about 11.7 million pounds, slightly better than the 11.3 million pounds expected for the year in previous trade estimates (**OPD's Chemical Marketing** 2/7/72, p. 17).

The production increase for 1971 as opposed to 1970 was on the order of 19 percent. In 1970, US producers made a little more than 9.8 million pounds of ascorbic.

In 1969, they made about 8.9 million pounds. By contrast with the 10 percent increase achieved by manufacturers here in 1970 the 19 percent advance in 1971, a year of vigorous demand and high prices, this represents a sharp gain.